

INVERSE PROBLEM FOR SUBDIFFUSION EQUATION

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Let $\rho \in (0,1]$. We study the inverse problem of finding functions $\{u(x,t), f(x)\}$ that satisfy the following problem

$$\begin{cases} D_t^\rho u(x,t) - \Delta u(x,t) = f(x)g(t), & x \in \Omega, \quad t \in (0,T], \\ u(x,t)|_{\partial\Omega} = 0, \\ u(x,0) = \varphi(x), \\ \int_0^T u(x,t)dt = \psi(x), & x \in \Omega. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here $f(x)$, $g(t)$ and $\varphi(x)$ are continuous functions in the domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^N$ and D_t^ρ stands for the Caputo fractional derivative.

In order to prove the existence of solutions of forward and inverse problems, it is necessary to study the convergence of the following series:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^\tau |h_k|^2, \quad \tau > \frac{N}{2}, \quad (2)$$

where h_k are the Fourier coefficients of function $h(x)$.

The theorem of V.A. Il'in states that, if function $h(x)$ satisfies the conditions

$$h(x) \in W_2^{\left[\frac{N}{2}\right]+1}(\Omega) \quad \text{and} \quad h(x), \Delta h(x), \dots, \Delta^{\left[\frac{N}{4}\right]} h(x) \in \dot{W}_2^1(\Omega), \quad (3)$$

then the number series (2) converges. Here $[a]$ denotes the integer part of the number a .

Similarly, if in (2) we replace τ by $\tau+2$, then the convergence conditions will have the form:

$$h(x) \in W_2^{\left[\frac{N}{2}\right]+3}(\Omega) \quad \text{and} \quad h(x), \Delta h(x), \dots, \Delta^{\left[\frac{N}{4}\right]+1} h(x) \in \dot{W}_2^1(\Omega). \quad (4)$$

Lemma 1. Let $\rho \in (0,1]$, $g(t) \in C[0,T]$ and $g(t) \neq 0$, $t \in [0,T]$. Then there is constant $C_0 > 0$, depending on T , such that for all k :

$$|p_{k,\rho}(T)| \geq \frac{C_0}{\lambda_k},$$

(5)

where

$$p_{k,\rho}(T) = \int_0^T (T-\eta)^\rho E_{\rho,\rho+1}(-\lambda_k(T-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta.$$

Lemma 2. Let $\rho \in (0,1]$, $g(t) \in C^1[0,T]$ and $g(0) \neq 0$. Then there exist numbers $m_0 > 0$ and k_0 such that, for all $T \leq m_0$ and $k \geq k_0$, the estimate (5) hold. Here constant C_0 depend on m_0 and k_0 .

Theorem 1. Let $\rho \in (0,1]$, $g(t) \in C[0,T]$ and $g(t) \neq 0$, $t \in [0,T]$. Moreover let function $\varphi(x)$ satisfy condition (3) and $\psi(x)$ satisfy condition (4). Then there exists a unique solution of the inverse problem (1):

$$f(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_{k,\rho}(T)} [\psi_k - \varphi_k TE_{\rho,2}(-\lambda_k T^\rho)] v_k(x),$$

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[\varphi_k E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) + \frac{b_{k,\rho}(t)}{p_{k,\rho}(T)} [\psi_k - \varphi_k TE_{\rho,2}(-\lambda_k T^\rho)] \right] v_k(x),$$

where

$$b_{k,\rho}(t) = \int_0^t (t-\eta)^{\rho-1} E_{\rho,\rho}(-\lambda_k(t-\eta)^\rho) g(\eta) d\eta.$$

Theorem 2. Let $\rho \in (0,1]$, $g(t) \in C^1[0,T]$, $g(0) \neq 0$ and T is sufficiently small. Moreover, function $\varphi(x)$ satisfy condition (3) and $\psi(x)$ satisfy condition (4).

If set $B_{0,\rho}$ is empty, i.e. $p_{k,\rho}(T) \neq 0$, for all k , then there exists a unique solution of the inverse problem (1).

If set $B_{0,\rho}$ is not empty, i.e. $p_{k,\rho}(T) = 0$, then for the existence of a solution to the inverse problem, it is necessary and sufficient that the following conditions

$$\psi_k = TE_{\rho,2}(-\lambda_k T^\rho) \varphi_k, \quad k \in B_{0,\rho}$$

be satisfied. In this case, the solution to the problem (1) exists, but is not unique:

$$f(x) = \sum_{k \in B_\rho} \frac{1}{p_{k,\rho}(T)} [\psi_k - \varphi_k TE_{\rho,2}(-\lambda_k T^\rho)] v_k(x) + \sum_{k \in B_{0,\rho}} f_k v_k(x),$$

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [\varphi_k E_{\rho,1}(-\lambda_k t^\rho) + b_{k,\rho}(t) f_k] v_k(x),$$

where f_k , $k \in B_{0,\rho}$, are arbitrary real numbers.

REFERENCES

1. V.A. Il'in. On the solvability of mixed problems for hyperbolic and parabolic equations // Russian Math. Surveys. **{\bf 15}**:2, 97-154 (1960).